

Broadband solar irradiation reflection by multilayer photonic structures with randomized layer thickness

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Abstract

Reflecting components based on photonic crystals that are optimized to reflect the Sun irradiation are very useful for energy applications. The employment of photonic structures as back reflectors in solar cells is widely studied. Moreover, photo-thermal effect employing photonic crystals to enhance photocatalysis is recently attracting increasing attention. Here, we show the efficient reflectivity of the whole solar irradiation spectrum with multilayer disordered photonic structures. To build a multilayer photonic structure that reflect a wide portion of the solar irradiation, a structure with a random distribution of layer thicknesses has been designed. A sequence of thicknesses for a 30-layer photonic structure, which allows a remarkable reflectance in the infrared part of the solar irradiation, has been determined with a proper algorithm. The angular dependence of the reflection of the photonic structure has been also studied. Such multilayers are made with Earth abundant materials, i.e., silicon dioxide and zirconium dioxide.

Keywords: Disordered photonic structures; solar irradiation; reflection optimization.

Introduction

In photovoltaic and photocatalytic systems, the employment of reflecting components based on photonic structures is widely studied to increase the efficiency of such solar devices. Just to give a brief overview of the first pioneering works in the field, in 2006 Zeng et al. have demonstrated a 19% increase of solar cell efficiency [1]. In 2007 O'Brien et al. have theoretically demonstrated enhanced photocurrent employing photonic crystals as back reflectors [2]. In 2008 O'Brien et al. have described the physical mechanisms that lead to absorption enhancement in silicon solar cells due to the use of photonic crystals [3]. Zhou et al. and Curtin et al., in 2008 and 2009, respectively, have designed photonic crystals as back reflectors to enhance the absorption of amorphous silicon solar cells [4,5]. In 2021, Duan et al. have demonstrated the improvement of the efficiency of heterojunction silicon solar cells with indium tin oxide/amorphous silicon photonic crystals [6]. Back reflectors based on photonic crystals are also very useful for photocatalytic devices. In 2018 and 2020, respectively, Low et al. and Chen et al. have employed a photonic crystal to reflect infrared radiation back to the photocatalytic system in order to increase the temperature and, consequently, the photocatalytic efficiency [7,8].

Broadband back-reflectors, that efficiently reflect the infrared portion of solar irradiation, are very useful for infrared photovoltaics and for photocatalysis. Noble metal mirrors are among the preferred devices for this kind of applications [9]. To avoid the use of expensive noble metal mirrors,

aperiodic metal/dielectric multilayer photonic structures with efficient reflection all over the solar irradiation spectrum [10].

Broadband reflection can be achieved in multilayer photonic structures with random layer thickness [11]. In this work, the efficient reflectivity of the solar irradiation, especially in the near infrared region, has been achieved by employing a multilayer photonic structure made with a randomized layer thickness sequence. The photonic structure has been designed with two oxides that include Earth abundant elements, i.e., silicon dioxide and zirconium dioxide [12]. An algorithm to find the layer thickness sequence, which corresponds to a photonic structure that efficiently reflects the solar irradiation, has been developed. The angular dependence of the light reflection of the photonic structure has been also studied.

Methods

The light reflection of the photonic structures designed in this work has been simulated with the transfer matrix method [11,13–16]. In this method, each k th layer of a certain material is described by a matrix that includes its refractive index d_k and its thickness n_k :

$$M_k = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} n_k(\lambda) d_k\right) & -\frac{i}{n_k(\lambda)} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} n_k(\lambda) d_k\right) \\ -i n_k(\lambda) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} n_k(\lambda) d_k\right) & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} n_k(\lambda) d_k\right) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

λ is the wavelength of the electromagnetic radiation (in nm). Thus, $n_k(\lambda)$ relates to the refractive index dispersion of the material. The thickness d_k is in nm.

The multilayer (with N layers) is described by the matrix given by the product of the matrixes of the layers:

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & M_{12} \\ M_{21} & M_{22} \end{bmatrix} = \prod_{k=1}^N M_k \quad (2)$$

The light reflection can be determined in the following way:

$$R = \frac{|(M_{11} + M_{12} n_0) n_s - (M_{21} + M_{22} n_0)|^2}{|(M_{11} + M_{12} n_0) n_s + (M_{21} + M_{22} n_0)|^2} \quad (3)$$

Where n_0 is the refractive index of air, while n_s is the refractive index of the substrate.

The refractive index dispersion can be described by the Sellmeier equation:

$$n_k^2(\lambda) - 1 = \sum_{j'=1} \frac{A_{j'} \lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - B_{j'}} \quad (4)$$

In Table 1 the parameters for silicon dioxide and zirconium dioxide are reported. In the Sellmeier equations, λ is in μm .

Material	A ₁	B ₁	A ₂	B ₂	A ₃	B ₃	Ref.
SiO ₂	0.6961663	0.0684043	0.4079426	0.1162414	0.8974794	9.896161	[17,18]
ZrO ₂	1.347091	0.062543	2.117788	0.166739	9.452943	24.32057	[19]

Table 1. Parameters of the Sellmeier equation for silicon dioxide and zirconium dioxide.

Results and Discussion

In Figure 1a the reflection spectrum of a 15-bilayer SiO₂/ZrO₂ photonic crystal (red curve) is shown. The layer thickness of all the layers is 200 nm. The photonic crystal shows a photonic band gap centred at about 1400 nm. In the studied spectral range, i.e., 300 – 2500 nm, the second, third, and fourth order of the photonic band gap at shorter wavelengths are observed in agreement with the Bragg-Snell law [20,21].

Figure 1. (a) Reflection spectra of a 15-bilayer SiO₂/ZrO₂ photonic crystal (red curve) and of a 15-bilayer SiO₂/ZrO₂ photonic structure with randomized layer thickness (black curve). (b) Normalized solar irradiation (direct and circumsolar irradiation [22], blue curve), reflection of the solar irradiation by the photonic crystal (red curve), and reflection of the solar irradiation by the photonic structure with randomized layer thickness (black curve).

The black curve in Figure 1a corresponds to the reflection spectrum of a 15-bilayer $\text{SiO}_2/\text{ZrO}_2$ photonic structure in which the thickness of each layer is $(100 + n)$ nm, where n is an integer between 0 and 200. In this way, the layer thickness spans from 100 and 300 nm. In previous works [11,23] it has been reported that these photonic structures show many reflection peaks (or transmission valleys) all over the studied spectral region.

In Figure 1b the normalized solar irradiation (direct and circumsolar irradiation [22]) is shown. With the simulated reflection spectra, it is possible to determine the portion of solar irradiation reflected by the two $\text{SiO}_2/\text{ZrO}_2$ photonic systems (red curve for the photonic crystal, black curve for the photonic structure with randomized layer thickness, respectively). For sake of clarity, the red curve is the product of the normalized solar irradiation and the reflection spectrum of the photonic crystal, while the black curve is the product of the normalized solar irradiation and the reflection spectrum of the photonic structure with randomized layer thickness. It is evident that the photonic structure with randomized layer thickness reflects the solar irradiation in a broader range.

Figure 2. Histogram of the integral of the reflection spectra for $\text{SiO}_2/\text{ZrO}_2$ photonic structure with different randomized layer thickness sequences (5000 different sequences).

A way to quantify the reflection efficiencies of the photonic system is the integral calculation of reflected normalized solar irradiation [i.e., $\text{integral}(R)$]. Such integral is simply calculated as the sum of the curve values with a step on 1 nm. For example, $\text{integral}(R)$ for the reflected normalized solar irradiation by the 15-bilayer $\text{SiO}_2/\text{ZrO}_2$ photonic crystal (red curve in Figure 1 below), is 188.4729. In Figure 2 the histogram of the integral of the reflection spectra for $\text{SiO}_2/\text{ZrO}_2$ photonic structure with 5000 different randomized layer thickness sequences is depicted. The histogram shows a peak at a value around 360.

To determine a photonic structure that efficiently reflects the infrared part of the solar irradiation, an algorithm has been here implemented. The flow chart of such algorithm is shown in Figure 3. In

the algorithm, the reflection spectra of photonic structures with different randomized layer thickness sequences are calculated until three conditions are not satisfied: i) $\text{integral}(R) > 400$; ii) reflection value at 1000 nm ($R_{1000 \text{ nm}} > 0.362$); iii) reflection value at 2100 nm ($R_{2100 \text{ nm}} > 0.045$). The optimized structure has an $\text{integral}(R)$ of 400.4231. Its layer thickness sequence (in nm) is 268, 277, 196, 252, 137, 184, 192, 297, 274, 266, 230, 283, 102, 156, 101, 128, 209, 136, 114, 260, 230, 286, 152, 126, 123, 109, 232, 151, 212, 152. The reflection spectrum of this structure is shown in Figure 4a (black solid curve). For a comparison, the reflection spectrum of the 15-bilayer $\text{SiO}_2/\text{ZrO}_2$ photonic crystal is shown in Figure 4a (red dashed curve).

Figure 3. Flow chart of the algorithm. The calculation runs until the three conditions in the decision block are not fulfilled.

An advantage of the randomized layer thickness based $\text{SiO}_2/\text{ZrO}_2$ photonic structure is that the two oxides show high electronic band gaps. In fact, the band gap of silicon dioxide is about 9 eV [24], while the band gap of zirconium dioxide is about 5 eV [25]. Thus, the only contribution of the photonic structure in the infrared region of the solar irradiation is due to reflection.

Figure 4. (a) Reflection spectra of a 15-bilayer SiO₂/ZrO₂ photonic crystal (red dashed curve) and the optimized 15-bilayer SiO₂/ZrO₂ photonic structure with randomized layer thickness found with the algorithm described in Figure 3 (black solid curve). (b) Normalized solar irradiation (direct and circumsolar irradiation [22], blue curve with blue area) and reflection of the solar irradiation by the optimized photonic structure with randomized layer thickness (black curve with yellow area).

In Figure 4b the blue curve with blue area corresponds to the Normalized solar irradiation (direct and circumsolar irradiation [22]), the black curve with yellow area corresponds to the reflection of the solar irradiation by the optimized photonic structure with randomized layer thickness. Such yellow area corresponds to the aforementioned $\int R$ of 400.4231. It is evident the wide portion of solar irradiation reflected by the structure. However, the light reflection spectrum optimized photonic structure with randomized layer thickness shows reflection valleys in the visible range and between 800 and 900 nm. The algorithm presented in this work can be better refined to optimize the reflection also in those ranges. Alternately, the photonic structure can be coupled to dielectric mirrors designed to reflect light in the range between 800 and 900 nm.

Figure 5. Angular dependence of the reflection spectrum of the optimized 15-bilayer $\text{SiO}_2/\text{ZrO}_2$ photonic structure with randomized layer thickness found with the algorithm described in Figure 3. Top: transverse electric (TE) waves; bottom: transverse magnetic (TM) waves.

Finally, in Figure 5 the angular dependence of the reflection spectrum of the optimized 15-bilayer $\text{SiO}_2/\text{ZrO}_2$ photonic structure with randomized layer thickness, found with the aforementioned algorithm, is shown. The simulation, calculated with a method in [26], has been performed for the transverse electric (TE) waves (Figure 5, top) and for the transverse magnetic (TM) waves (Figure 5, bottom). It is evident the blue shift of the peaks, in agreement with the Bragg-Snell law [20], and the narrowing of the reflection peaks for TM waves.

Conclusion

Mirrors based on photonic structures can be employed as back reflectors for photovoltaic and photocatalytic devices as a low-cost alternative to noble metal-based mirrors. A broadband reflection with these optical components is beneficial for the afore mentioned applications. In this work, an algorithm to optimize the fabrication of a multilayer photonic structure, in which the layer thickness is randomized, has been developed. The angular dependence of the light reflection of the above-mentioned optimised photonic structure was simulated with an appropriate algorithm, showing the blue shift of the reflection peaks and the narrowing of the peaks for TM polarisation. The photonic structure has been designed by using silicon dioxide and zirconium dioxide, which include low-cost and Earth-abundant elements.

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